

Investigation of applications of nanotechnology in industrial wastewater treatment

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Abstract

One of the biggest human challenges today is access to safe drinking water. Due to limited access to safe water resources and the development of human societies, the growing need to purify and purify natural water resources is felt more than ever. In this way, various methods for removing water pollutants have been proposed, each of which has its own disadvantages and advantages. The present article tries to introduce the most important pollutants in groundwater, surface water and drinking water in detail and to examine the destructive effects of each of them on human health and the natural cycle of the Earth's ecosystem. This article is a prelude to the discussion of water purification and desalination.

Keywords: Wastewater treatment, wastewater, nanotechnology, drinking water